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HYPOTHYROIDISM IN PATIENTS WITH PCOS AND ABNORMAL LIPID PROFILE: AN INTERVENTIONAL APPROACH USING HOMEOPATHIC MEDICAL REPERTORY

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Abstract

Two common anomalies in women include thyroid conditions and polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS). Although the cause of these disorders is unknown, there seems to be a correlation. It is still unclear exactly how hypothyroidism and PCOS are related. Clinical signs, overlapping symptoms, as well as reproductive and metabolic traits, help to identify them. A decrease in infertility as well as an increase in insulin and cholesterol levels have been associated with both illnesses. In PCOS women, hypothyroidism and autoimmune thyroid disease are found to occur significantly more frequently. On the other hand, PCOS and hypothyroidism have detrimental effects on lipid profiles and can result in metabolic syndromes and cardiovascular problems. The treatment time may be increased due to the disagreement over the lipid profile variation in hypothyroidism and PCOS. The study aimed to determine how individuals with hypothyroidism and PCOS differ in their lipid profiles and the clinical value of Homeopathic medical repertory in the treatment of hypothyroidism, PCOS, and aberrant lipid profiles. Among the 15 cases of hypothyroidism with PCOS, there are alterations in the lipid profile, particularly in total cholesterol (TC), Low-density Lipoprotein (LDL), and triglycerides (TGL), and a minor decline in High-density lipoprotein (HDL) in a very small number of cases. A total of 12 cases from mild to marked showed improvement after the research period, whereas 3 cases showed no improvement. Using Murphy Repertory, the prescription was individualized and repertorized thoroughly.

Keywords: Cardiovascular disease, Hypothyroidism, Lipid Profile, Metabolism, Murphy repertory.

INTRODUCTION

Hypothyroidism is one of the endocrine conditions that affect young women most frequently. A range of clinical hypo-metabolism symptoms and signs are caused by a lack of thyroid hormone secretion and activity, which is how it is described^(1,2). Children that have a hypo-functioning experience “Cretinism,” which is characterized by a lack of intellectual and physical development. In comparison to men, women are more likely to get

hypothyroidism. The body experiences a wide range of symptoms due to thyroid gland failure (hypo-function), including mental and physical lassitude. The symptoms could be caused by decreased hormone synthesis or by the effects of decreasing thyroid hormone in the target tissue. They experience monthly irregularities, either in excess, known as menorrhagia, or infrequently, known as amenorrhoea, as well as tiredness, cold sensitivity, and rapid weight gain. They could also exhibit desperation and fear. Hypothyroidism in early pregnancy increases the risk of pre-eclampsia, stillbirth, and cretinous offspring^(3,4).

Most women of reproductive age now experience PCOS, an endocrinological condition. It is characterized by ovarian malfunction, which can lead to irregular menstrual periods or amenorrhea, hyperandrogenism and/or hyperandrogenemia, polycystic ovary/ovaries, and, in many cases, illnesses including insulin resistance, hyperinsulinemia, obesity (noticeable mainly in the waist circumference and BMI), hypertension, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), infertility, hirsutism (5,6).

In short, the etiopathogenesis of PCOS and hypothyroidism are significantly different. Women with PCOS have a higher prevalence of thyroid abnormalities than people in general, especially hypothyroidism (7-10). Between 5% and 10% of PCOS patients experience thyroid gland abnormalities, with hypothyroidism, particularly subclinical hypothyroidism (11). SCH, a milder form of hypothyroidism, can result in infertility and unfavorable pregnancy outcomes even though it may not show any overt clinical symptoms. Infertility, dyslipidemia, and irregular menstruation are now quite frequent in women with PCOS and hypothyroidism. Metabolic syndrome is characterized by a broad variety of symptoms that can appear in various combinations and with various intensities, and as a result, it develops into a fully developed condition over time (12-15).

Women with PCOS usually have lipid abnormalities such as high triglyceride levels, low HDL levels, and high non-HDL levels. PCOS is associated with obesity, insulin resistance, and hyperandrogenism, all of which have unique and interactive effects on dyslipidemia, while the mechanisms behind these interactions remain unknown (16). In obese individuals without PCOS, it appears to be either independent of or in addition to insulin resistance (17). Dyslipidemia is associated with PCOS, even though not all women with the disorder have Insulin Resistance. There are numerous causes of dyslipidemia in PCOS. Studies for decreasing CVD (cardiovascular disease) have focused on the significance of dyslipidemia as the primary proximate cause of atherosclerosis and, as a result, vascular diseases, as well as factors contributing to PCOS dyslipidemia.

Most individuals with hypothyroidism have few or no signs of thyroid problems. According to a large cross-sectional study, patients with hypothyroidism have noticeably higher total cholesterol levels than euthyroid adults when their blood TSH levels are much higher. It is currently unclear whether other lipid markers including blood LDL, HDL, and triglyceride levels are useful. Studies have shown that people with hypothyroidism have a different lipid profile, with high LDL levels and low HDL levels (18,19). The onset of biochemical abnormalities, peripheral vascular disease, and coronary artery disease are only a few of the conditions that are linked to hypothyroidism. Abnormalities in lipid profiles and overt hypothyroidism are known to be related.

In summary, a high incidence of dyslipidemia, one of the most prevalent cardiovascular risk factors, is associated with both PCOS and hypothyroidism. However, there are merely a few research examining the differences in lipid variables in people with PCOS and hypothyroidism, and the results are inconsistent. The purpose of this study was to compare the endocrine and lipid profiles of PCOS patients who also had hypothyroidism, as well as how they were treated with homeopathic treatments by Murphy's Repertory and the homeopathic principle.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of samples

In our study, we chose 15 samples of post-pubertal women between the ages of 20 and 45 who had complained of irregular menstruation or infertility to Sarada Krishna Homeopathic Medical College and Hospital, and rural centers of Sarada Krishna Medical College and had ultrasound evidence of polycystic ovaries and confirmed hypothyroidism. The Institution's ethics committee has given its clearance for the conduct of this study. In this study, patients with an acute emergency are not included, nor are women who are taking oral contraceptives, anticonvulsants, or other illnesses that may mimic PCOS.

Study design:

A single-blinded, prospective clinical study without a control group.

Processing, and blood collection

Age, height, weight, and body fat were among the clinical data we gathered, and the following measurements: were hip circumference, waist circumference, and the ratio of Waist to Hips (WHR). The blood samples were collected after 8 hours of fasting. Plasma total TGL, TC, HDL, LDL, and TSH concentrations were assessed. The prescription will be made based on the symptom similarities of Murphy's repertory (Homoeopathic medical repertory) as an intervention in Computer software Zomeo and by referring to Materia medica after thorough case history, physical exam, and further investigation (if needed).

Data analysis

Data analysis was performed on the collected data using statistical computer software (Microsoft Excel).

Statistical techniques

Pre and post-test values of TSH and Lipid profile were subjected to a statistical test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to other literature, treating an autoimmune condition, hormone imbalance, and variation in lipid profile as such is very tough. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the Murphy repertory's effectiveness in treating hypothyroidism with PCOS by examining changes in lipid profiles in this condition. Repertorizing using the Murphy Repertory, however, improved lipid profiles, symptomatically improved PCOS cases, and instances of hypothyroidism by a moderate to considerable margin. Additionally, this research demonstrates that lipid abnormalities are present in almost all circumstances.

This study discovered that women between the ages of 20 - 30 (73.3%) and 30 - 40 (26.7%), which includes 10 out of 15 (66.7%), have the highest prevalence of hypothyroidism with PCOS. According to a study published in 2020, abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB), the most common monthly irregularity, occurs in about 15-20% of women in the reproductive age range of 15 to 45 years. Abnormalities in menstruation typically appear before overt hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism manifests themselves (20). This study shows that the condition of hypothyroidism with PCOS is more common in people between the ages of 20 and 30. Therefore, the age group is very relevant to the study group, as shown by our study and the study carried out in 2020.

According to the waist/hip ratio, six (40%) ladies have a low risk of developing health problems, five (33.3%) have a moderate risk, four (26.7%) have a high risk and according to BMI 10, 66.7 percent of females are overweight, although PCOS can be detected in both fat and thin people. A 2019 study, says that claims that a waist-to-hip ratio of 0.87 indicates the existence of central obesity, a symptom of PCOS (21). According to a 2012 study, the hypothyroid group experienced a marked increase in BMI and WHR whereas the hyperthyroid group experienced a marked decrease in BMI. This shows that PCOS in hypothyroidism patients can belong to any of the three categories, albeit it tends to belong to the overweight category more frequently and increases in BMI(22).

Fig 1: Distribution of cases according to TSH level in comparison with pre and post-test values

This report shows, TSH levels improved in 13 of the 15 cases, representing 86.6% of the study group, and did not improve in 2, representing 13.3% of the study group. The results were within the usual range in 13 cases. In a 2014 study, 19 (25.5%) of them had TSH levels above 3.75, normal FT3 and FT4 values, and history of SCH. On the other side, 56 cases (74.4%) of euthyroidism were discovered. (23). A higher incidence of SCH has been associated with PCOS, according to a study published in 2020, a significant association between SCH and PCOS sufferers. According to the results of our study, SCH significantly affected the clinical, metabolic, and hormonal characteristics of PCOS patients. This may be due to insulin resistance in PCOS being exacerbated by subclinical hypothyroidism(24). As a result, even in the absence of symptoms linked to thyroid dysfunction,

screening for a thyroid issue in PCOS patients is advised because it may benefit the patient clinically and demonstrates how homeopathy effectively lowers Thyroid Stimulating Hormone.

Fig 2: Distribution of cases according to Total cholesterol level in comparison with pre and post-test values

In 15 cases, 5 cases have total cholesterol levels that are within the normal range, and 9 cases have total cholesterol levels that are above normal. After taking medicine, total cholesterol levels decreased in 11 cases, whereas they increased in 4 cases (2 of which had normal levels and 2 of which had levels above the normal range). Overall, the total cholesterol level decreased in 73.3% of the study subjects.

Fig 3: Distribution of cases according to Low-density Lipid level in comparison with pre and post-test values

Six of the 15 cases had normal LDL levels, and nine have readings that are above normal. After taking the drug, the LDL level rose in 6 cases and fell in 9 cases. 60% of the study group saw improvement overall after taking medicine in 9 cases, as evidenced by a drop in LDL levels.

Fig 4: Distribution of cases according to High-density Lipid level in comparison with pre and post-test values

All of the observations among the 15 cases fall within the range of a normal level. Following treatment, the HDL level decreased in 3 cases, while it increased in 12 other cases, all of which fall within the normal range. In general, 80% of cases improve, increasing HDL levels.

Fig 5: Distribution of cases according to very low-density level in comparison with pre and post-test values

Of the 15 cases, only one falls within the normal range, while the other 14 falls into the above-normal range. 13 cases show a decrease in VLDL level after medication, whereas 2 cases show an increase. In total, 2 patients reached a normal level, and 11 cases were above average but had their VLDL levels reduced, improving 86.6% of the research group

Fig 6: Distribution of cases according to Triglycerides in comparison with pre and post-test values

Four of the 15 instances had normal TGL levels, whereas the other 11 cases have TGL values that are higher than the normal range. After treatment, 2 cases exhibit higher TGL values than usual, whereas the other 13 cases show level TGL values. In those 8 cases, the level reached normal, while in the other 5 cases, the reduction is still over normal. Overall, 13 cases (86.6% of the study group) indicate improvement or a decrease in TGL Value.

Fig 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 show the variation of each component in lipid profile i.e. variation in TC, LDL, HDL, VLDL, and TGL. The results of a study done in 2014 showed that there was no difference in the levels of TG in the various groups. When TSH levels were raised, there was a trend toward higher TC and LDLc and lower HDLc, only the changes in TC and LDLc levels were statistically significant across the five categories. Furthermore, there was a strong positive correlation between serum TSH and LDL (15).

In short, there are lipid profile variations in our investigations, particularly higher-than-normal levels of triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein, and total cholesterol.

Fig 7: Distribution of cases according to Medicines prescribed

Among the 15 cases, Sepia was given in 4 cases, (26.6%) Calcarea carb and Thuja in 3 cases,(20%) Natrum muriaticum in 2 cases (13.3%) and Pulsatilla, Lycopodium, and Staphysagria in each case (6.7%). A similar study conducted on PCOS has also prescribed Natrum Mur, Pulsatilla, Lycopodium, Calcarea Carb, and Sepia(25). The most often prescribed medications in another study on hypothyroidism were Pulsatilla and Natrum muriaticum(26).

Fig 8:Distribution of cases according to Potency

The study population was divided into 15 cases: 10 cases received 200 potencies, representing 66.7% of the study group, 3 cases received 1M potencies, representing 20% of the study population and 2 cases received 0/3 potency, representing 13.3% of the study population.

Fig 9: Distribution of cases according to the improvement

Five of the fifteen instances (33.3%) showed a strong improvement, four (27%), a moderate improvement, three (20%), a light improvement, and three (20%) no improvement. This demonstrates a beneficial effect of homeopathic treatment along with lifestyle modification demonstrates an improvement in the case of hypothyroidism with PCOS and lipid profile from mild to noticeable.

CONCLUSION

A considerable improvement was seen in five of the fifteen cases (33.3%), a moderate improvement in four (27%), a light improvement in three (20%), and no improvement in three (20%). This reveals a positive effect of homeopathic treatment because it shows a change from mild to evident in the case of hypothyroidism with PCOS and lipid profile. As, a result, the medications chosen after repertorization utilizing the Murphy repertory and lifestyle modification have a good impact on variations of aberrant lipid profiles and hypothyroidism with PCOS.

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